

Perception of Entrepreneurship Among Hospitality Students

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Abstract:

This research examines hospitality students' perceptions of entrepreneurship and the factors influencing their interest in starting their own ventures. A survey was conducted among students from different year levels. The findings indicate that the majority of students are familiar with concept of entrepreneurship in hospitality industry. Financial independence and passion emerged as the primary motivations for pursuing entrepreneurship. Overall, the study highlights a positive entrepreneurial mindset among hospitality students and suggests the need for universities to strengthen entrepreneurial education and support systems.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, ventures, training, workshops, financial support, mentorship, training, motivation.

Introduction

The hospitality industry known for its diverse and creativity, thrives on innovation and service excellence. Hospitality students play crucial role to represents future professionals. Their perception influences not only their career choices but also the future direction of the industry. Entrepreneurship emerged to drive transformation within this sector, introducing new startup models, guest experiences and sustainable practices. There is a growing recognition that future leaders must not only passes operational skills but also an entrepreneurial mindset that how capable of identifying opportunities, managing risks and creating values. Sectors such as hospitality, leisure, sports and tourism can be seen as archetypal entrepreneurial industries and can consequently play a key role in economic development.

Objectives

To assess student's interests in starting their own hospitality ventures.

To identify factors that encourage or discourage entrepreneurship.

To propose strategies for universities to support student entrepreneurship.

Review of Literature

Simpsons , Grache and K.Ayeh(2022)

According to the authors, the entrepreneurship is a growing and prominent component of hospitality and tourism education worldwide. Starting a business is risky due to an unpredictable business environment, inadequate governmental support, and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic.

J. Mustafa^a, Craig Lee^b, Galloway^c (2023)

This theory emphasizes the crucial role of the university climate is shaping entrepreneurial intentions. the study uses social cognitive career theory and institutional theory to examine how entrepreneurial climates affect as well as student’s self-efficacy and outcome expectations are crucial factors influenced by the university environment.

Manoj kumar, Ramaprasad, Nidhish Rao & Mohit jamwal(2022)

According to the author, students feel the entrepreneurial education is effective, it increases their self-confidence. Their higher self confidence leads to stronger entrepreneurial intentions which means ESE acts as bridge between entrepreneurial education and its entrepreneurial intention.

James, Edopkolor , Okolie(2021)

This author’s research has shown that when students believe entrepreneurship is desirable and achievable, their confidence in entrepreneurial tasks increases. When students feel that starting a business is desirable and feasible, their self confidence strengthens, which ultimately leads to stronger entrepreneurial intentions.

Dr.Chinthala kishore kumar(2025)

The author shows how rapidly women entrepreneurship increasing day by day in business administration where government play their crucial role to support special schemes like subsidies and grants to motivate women entrepreneur. Women participate not only in tourism but also in education, healthcare, defence and business.

Research Methodology

This research project based on the perceptions of entrepreneurship among hospitality students. The data is collected from undergraduate students who are pursuing hotel management degree programme. During research, the questionnaires were used with different rating methods, which comes under primary and secondary data collection technique. Moreover, qualities assessed by applying quantitative research method.

Calculation And Analysis

Fig.1

(Fig.1) This indicates the sample population is almost balanced, with only a small difference between participations. 55.6% of the respondents are Male, 44.4%of the female respondents.

Questions	Categories	%
Familiarity with concept of entrepreneurship in hospitality industry	Very familiar	57.8
	Somehow familiar	17.8
	Not clear	20
	Not familiar	4
Importance of entrepreneurship for hospitality industry growth	Strongly agree	37.8
	Agree	51.1
	neutral	11.1
	Disagree	0
Motivation to become an entrepreneur	Financial independent	46.7
	Passion	40
	Job insecurity	13.3
	Family business	Very low

Table 1

The survey reveals second year students highly participated in survey (60%) followed by third year (30%) whereas first and final year students shows less interested .

Table 1. indicates that most students posses strong awareness of entrepreneurship. However, there is still a portion of respondents who need more clarity and exposure to the concept. This suggests scope to organize more workshops, seminars, and practical learning opportunities.

The next finding shows positive perception towards entrepreneurship. A combined 88.9% believe entrepreneurship plays very important role in rise of hospitality industry.

The data suggests about their primary reason for wanting to pursue entrepreneurship is the financial freedom which is the strongest motivating factors among hospitality students, followed by a genuine interests in the hospitality field. Moreover, job insecurity also plays a role, indicating that some of the students prefer entrepreneurship as a more consistent and independent career path.

Interest level	%
Yes, definitely	44.4
Maybe in future	42.2
Not sure	8.9
Not at all	4.4
TOTAL	99.9

(Table1.1) indicates high propensity for entrepreneurship among into students. A significant majority of respondents shows keen interest to startup their own business, with 44.4% stating they would YES, definitely do so. Only a small fraction of respondents.

Table.1.1

Area of hospitality	%
Food and beverage	28.9
Accommodation	2.2
Event management	17.8
Travel and tourism	20.0

Others	31.0
TOTAL	99.9

(Tables1.2) illustrates the diverse area of hospitality attracts the students. The highest percentage of students, 31.0%, were attracted to OTHERS. Among specific areas, (food and beverage service) attracted the largest group at 28.9% that rest of all areas. While ACCOMODATION was the least attractive sector for starting a venture(2.2%).

Table.1.2

(Table1.3) highlights the primary barriers perceived by students when considering the launch of enterprise. An overwhelming 51.1% of respondents cited LESS EXPERIENCE as their biggest challenge. FEAR OF FAILIURE and GOVERNMENT RULES/REGULATIONS were less prevalent concerns, which is 17.8% and 11.1% of respondents .

Challenges	%
Lack of capital	20.0
Less experience	51.1
Fear of failiure	17.8
Government rules/regulations	11.1
TOTAL	100.0

just

Table 1.3

Type of suport	%
Loans / grants	15.6
Mentorship/training	48.9
Business network	24.4
Workshops	11.1
TOTAL	100.0

Table 1.4

(Table1.4) specifies the preferred forms of support students would like to receive to facilitate their entrepreneurial journey. The highest demand, at 48.9% was for MENTORSHIP/TRAINING. This aligns with previous findings that LESS EXPERIENCE is the primary challenge for hospitality students, while WORKSHOPS were the least

preferred option at 11.1%.

Likelihood	%
Very likely	40.0
Somewhat likely	42.2
Not likely	15.4
Not at all	15.0

(Table1.5) measures the likelihood of students pursuing entrepreneurship immediately after completing their studies. It reveals in data that the hospitality students SOMEWHAT LIKE to pursue businessman skills after completion of their graduation period, however participants shows less number of ratio to not to start their venture after degree. The data depicts students largely focus on their own

Table 1.5

startup immediately after graduation.

Moving further, one specific mechanism suggested by students for promoting entrepreneurship by organizing more competitions at colleges, with proper guidance from experts as well as proper funding to support students to start their ventures in hospitality field. This finding suggests a demand for structured, physical spaces and support systems to help translate business ideas into reality.

Conclusion

The research concludes that hospitality students hold positive perception of entrepreneurship and recognize its importance in the growth of the hospitality industry. The majority respondents are familiar with entrepreneurial concepts and express a strong desire for financial independence, which is the biggest driver behind their entrepreneurial intentions. Therefore, educational institutions should focus on organizing workshops, seminars, mentorship programs, and training to further strengthen students'

entrepreneurial skills and confidence. Enhancing such support can encourage more hospitality students to transform their ideas into successful business ventures.

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